

DEVELOPMENT OF A MULTICULTURAL DIGITAL STORYTELLING FLIPBOOK TO IMPROVE ELEMENTARY STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS AND TOLERANCE

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Abstract

This study aims to develop a multicultural-based Flipbook Digital Storytelling to enhance speaking skills and intercultural social tolerance among third-grade elementary school students. The needs analysis conducted at SDN 017 Penajam revealed that students lacked confidence in speaking, the use of digital media was still low, and learning remained focused on textbooks. In addition, misunderstandings frequently occurred in intercultural interactions. Therefore, an interactive learning media that integrates multicultural values, audio, visuals, and narrative elements is urgently needed. This study involved 96 third-grade students and employed a Research and Development (R&D) design using the ADDIE model. Data were collected through speaking skill tests, social tolerance scales, observations, interviews, and expert validations. Data analysis included qualitative analysis, validity, practicality, and effectiveness assessments. The findings indicate that the developed media is highly valid (material expert = 3.57; language expert = 3.41; media expert = 3.60). It is also highly practical, as shown by teacher responses (92%), student responses (89%), and classroom observations (85%). Speaking skills improved from 63 to 83, while social tolerance increased from 68% to 84%, with an N-Gain score of 0.47. Thus, the multicultural-based Flipbook Digital Storytelling has been proven valid, practical, and effective in improving students' speaking abilities as well as fostering appreciation and tolerance toward cultural diversity.

Keywords: *Flipbook, Multicultural, Speak, Tolerance.*

INTRODUCTION

In today's modern era, education plays an essential role in improving the intellectual quality of a nation. Multicultural education has become highly relevant in elementary schools due to Indonesia's diversity in ethnicity, language, culture, and religion. This diversity is both a strength and a challenge, requiring learning strategies that can instill respect and appreciation within a pluralistic society. Multicultural education emphasizes the importance of strengthening values such as tolerance, empathy, and social integration, which are crucial in elementary learning (Inayatul Ummah et al., 2025; Rahmawati et al., 2025). Digital transformation in education has encouraged the emergence of more interactive learning media, one of which is digital storytelling that integrates visuals, audio, and narrative (Puspitasari et al., 2025). Digital learning media such as flipbooks are considered capable of increasing student engagement through appealing illustrations, audio, and animations (Istiq'faroh et al., 2022; Yolanita et al., 2025). Such media hold great potential to enhance speaking skills—defined as the ability to express ideas and feelings orally in a coherent and confident manner (Pratiwi, 2016; Andini et al., 2024). However, in practice, elementary school students, particularly third graders, still struggle to tell stories sequentially, tend to be passive when asked to speak, and show low confidence in communication.

Moreover, interactions among students from different cultural backgrounds often lead to misunderstandings, jokes that verge on mockery, and social awkwardness. This indicates that values of intercultural tolerance have not been optimally developed. Yet tolerance is a crucial character trait that must be instilled early to build harmonious interpersonal relationships (Yumnafiska et al., 2023; Wibowo, 2024). A needs analysis conducted through interviews on October 15, 2025, at SD Negeri 017 Penajam reinforced the importance of developing digital-based learning media. The school was selected because of its high cultural diversity, including Bugis, Javanese, Banjar, Toraja, and Paser communities. At SD Negeri 017, teachers still rely on textbooks and worksheets as primary learning resources.

Speaking activities are limited to simple question-and-answer sessions, without opportunities for students to tell

stories or engage in culturally contextual dialogues. The learning media used tend to be monotonous, lacking audio-visual components, and do not integrate multicultural values. As a result, students feel shy about speaking in front of the class and struggle to construct sentences coherently. These findings highlight the need for interactive learning media that combine visual elements, audio, and multicultural narratives. The Digital Storytelling Flipbook becomes a potential solution because it allows the presentation of illustrated stories accompanied by audio narration relevant to students' lives. This media can feature local and national folklore, characters from various cultures, and retelling activities that train speaking skills while fostering intercultural social tolerance.

Digital storytelling has been proven to improve students' speaking skills and enrich learning experiences through multimodality, combining listening, reading, speaking, and writing elements (Yuniarti et al., 2022; Solichah, 2022; Marsiana et al., 2025). Meanwhile, digital flipbooks enable the delivery of content with text, images, animations, audio, and videos in a single medium (Anengsih et al., 2025). Such media have been shown to improve students' motivation, learning outcomes, and communication skills (Widjayanti et al., 2024; Riska Andriani et al., 2024; Umama et al., 2025). Indonesia's rich cultural diversity makes the development of multicultural-based digital media a valuable effort to preserve local culture and strengthen students' identity (Istiq'faroh et al., 2024; Zhussupova et al., 2023). Integrating multicultural aspects into digital storytelling flipbooks will help students understand cultural diversity through stories that are relatable to their everyday experiences.

Although digital media have been widely developed, their implementation in elementary learning is still dominated by conventional approaches. There is a lack of research specifically focusing on developing multicultural digital storytelling flipbooks designed to improve both speaking skills and intercultural social tolerance simultaneously. Therefore, this study is important as it offers media innovation that not only focuses on language aspects but also strengthens students' multicultural character. Thus, this research aims to develop a Multicultural Digital Storytelling Flipbook as a learning medium to improve speaking skills and foster intercultural social tolerance among third-grade elementary school students. This media is expected to contribute theoretically to the literature on digital education and practically support teachers in delivering creative, interactive learning that aligns with the characteristics of the digital generation and Indonesia's cultural diversity.

METHOD

This study employed a Research and Development (R&D) approach by adapting the ADDIE development model (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation). This approach was chosen because the objective of the research is to produce a multicultural-based Flipbook Digital Storytelling learning media that is valid, practical, and effective for Indonesian language learning in elementary schools. In addition, the study used mixed methods, consisting of qualitative data (interviews, observations, expert comments) and quantitative data (expert validation, questionnaires, speaking skills tests, and intercultural social tolerance scales). The research was conducted at SD Negeri 017 Penajam, Penajam Paser Utara Regency, East Kalimantan, during the first semester of the 2025/2026 academic year (October 2025–February 2026). The research subjects consisted of 96 third-grade students and third-grade teachers who served as validators and users of the media. The subjects were selected using purposive sampling based on relevance to the research objectives and the implementation of the Merdeka Curriculum.

The research procedure followed the five stages of ADDIE. The analysis stage was carried out to identify the needs of teachers and students, the conditions of Indonesian language learning, and the need for multicultural media. The design stage included the development of storyboards, story flow, layouts, and visual designs of the Flipbook Digital Storytelling. The development stage covered the creation of the media using a digital flipbook platform and validation by material experts, language experts, and media experts. The implementation stage was conducted through a limited trial in two third-grade classrooms to obtain practicality data and user responses. The evaluation stage was conducted formatively at each stage and summatively based on trial results to assess the validity, practicality, and effectiveness of the product.

The operational definitions of variables in this study include:

- 1) Flipbook Digital Storytelling, an interactive learning media that integrates text, images, audio, and video to deliver multicultural-based stories.
- 2) Speaking skills, the students' ability to express ideas orally with indicators of clarity of speech, fluency, word accuracy, and intonation.
- 3) Intercultural social tolerance, the attitude of accepting differences, cooperating within diversity, demonstrating social empathy, and respecting the cultural identities of others.

DEVELOPMENT F A MULTICULTURAL DIGITAL STORYTELLING FLIPBOOK TO IMPROVE ELEMENTARY STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS AND TOLERANCE

Salmawati et al

The instruments used in this study include teacher interviews, learning observations, expert validation questionnaires, teacher and student response questionnaires, speaking skills tests, and an intercultural social tolerance attitude scale. Interviews and observations were used during the analysis stage to gather media-related needs. Expert validation was used to assess the feasibility of the product in terms of content, language, and design. Response questionnaires were used to assess the practicality of the media during learning. Speaking skills tests and tolerance scales were administered before and after the use of the media to evaluate the effectiveness of the Flipbook Digital Storytelling.

The data analysis techniques were carried out in three aspects. First, validity analysis was assessed using the average score of a Likert scale (1–4) and qualitatively reviewed based on validator comments. Second, practicality analysis was obtained from teacher and student questionnaire results and observations of the learning process, calculated using the practicality percentage. Third, effectiveness analysis was conducted by calculating speaking skills scores, intercultural social tolerance scores, and N-Gain to measure improvement between the pretest and posttest. Qualitative data was analyzed using the Miles and Huberman model through data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing. Through the ADDIE development procedure and the applied analytical techniques, this study ensures that the resulting Flipbook Digital Storytelling meets the criteria of being valid, practical, and effective as multicultural learning media for third-grade elementary school students.

Data Analysis Techniques

Table 1. Media Validity Analysis

Component	Analysis Technique	Formula	Criteria
Material Expert Validation	Likert Scale 1–4	$V = \frac{\sum \text{score}}{\sum \text{maximum score}}$	3.26–4.00 = Very Valid 2.51–3.25 = Valid 1.76–2.50 = Less Valid 1.00–1.75 = Not Valid
Media/Design Expert Validation	Average score	Total score per validator	Valid if score ≥ 2.51
Language & Multicultural Expert Validation	Quantitative descriptive	Overall average	Revision based on validator comments

Table 2. Media Practicality Analysis

Component	Instrument	Analysis Technique	Formula	Criteria
Teacher Response	Likert Questionnaire	Practicality Percentage	$P = \left(\frac{\sum \text{score}}{\sum \text{maximum score}} \right) \times 100\%$	86–100% = Very Practical 71–85% = Practical 56–70% = Fairly Practical 40–55% = Less Practical
Student Response	Likert / Visual Questionnaire	Percentage	Same formula	Practical if $\geq 71\%$
Learning Observation	Observation Sheet	Quantitative Descriptive	$\text{Score} / \text{total} \times 100\%$	Good if $\geq 75\%$

Media Effectiveness Analysis

Table 3. Intercultural Speaking Skills and Social Tolerance Test

Component	Instrument	Analysis Technique	Formula	Criteria
Speaking Skills	Performance Rubric	Percentage	Score = $(\sum \text{score} / \text{maximum score}) \times 100\%$	$\geq 80\%$ = Excellent 70–79% = Good 60–69% = Fair < 60% = Poor
Intercultural Social Tolerance	Observation Rubric	Percentage of Improvement	Same formula	Effective if $\geq 75\%$

N-Gain Analysis

Table 4. N-Gain Analysis

Component	Analysis Technique	Formula	Category
Learning Improvement	N-Gain	$N\text{-Gain} = (\text{Post} - \text{Pre}) / (\text{Max} - \text{Pre})$	> 0.70 = High 0.30–0.70 = Medium < 0.30 = Low
Media Effectiveness	Score Comparison	N-Gain Value	Effective if category \geq Medium

Qualitative Data Analysis

Table 5. Qualitative Data Analysis

Component	Data Source	Analysis Technique	Steps
Expert Comments	Validation sheets	Miles & Huberman	Data reduction → Data display → Conclusion drawing
Teacher & Student Observation	Observation sheets	Reduction & categorization	Identifying constraints & responses
Product Revision Suggestions	Validators & teachers	Content analysis	Basis for product revision

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Findings

The focus of this research is to improve the speaking skills and intercultural social tolerance of third-grade elementary school students through the digital learning media product Flipbook. Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation are all part of the ADDIE model used to guide the development process. The research results for each phase are shown here.

1. Phase Analysis Results: Learning needs for SDN 017 Penajam were identified through teacher interviews, lesson observations, and curriculum documentation.
 - a. Teacher and Student Needs Analysis: Interviews conducted on October 15, 2025, indicated that teachers still relied on textbooks and worksheets. Learning media lacked variety and did not contain audio, visual, or cultural elements. Third-grade students still struggled to speak coherently, remained shy, and passive. Interactions between students of diverse cultures often resulted in teasing jokes. There was no available media that explicitly integrated multicultural aspects.
 - b. Indonesian Language Learning Analysis: A simple question-and-answer method was used in speaking lessons; teachers had not used a storytelling approach digital stories; and students did not have opportunities to tell stories orally.
 - c. Multicultural Media Needs Analysis: Students come from Bugis, Javanese, Banjar, Toraja, and Paser cultural backgrounds. Teacher stories do not reflect the students' cultural diversity. Interactive media that presents multicultural and contextual stories is needed.

Conclusion of the Analysis Phase: To improve students' speaking skills and intercultural social tolerance, digital flipbooks containing multicultural narratives are essential.

Table 6. Needs Analysis Results (Interviews and Observations)

No.	Aspect Analyzed	Field Findings	Learning Implications
1	Learning Media	Teachers still use textbooks and worksheets as the main sources. No audio-visual media.	The need for engaging, interactive, and multimodal digital media.
2	Students' Speaking Skills	Students are passive, shy to speak, and have difficulty organizing stories coherently.	Media that supports retelling and oral practice.
3	Cultural Diversity	Students come from Bugis, Javanese, Toraja, Banjar, and Paser backgrounds.	Media should include multicultural content.
4	Tolerance Learning	There are cases of jokes leading to mockery and misunderstandings.	Media should foster empathy and understanding of other cultures.
5	Technology Use	No digital storytelling in use.	Digital flipbooks as an innovative solution.

2. Design Stage Results

In the design stage, researchers developed the media concept and structure, including:

- Storyboards using storylines and characters from various Indonesian cultures.
- Visual designs using bright colors, easy-to-understand icons, and child-friendly navigation.
- Incorporating multimodal elements such as story text, audio narration, illustrations, and light animations.
- Instrument development: expert validation questionnaire, speaking rubric, social tolerance scale, teacher-student response questionnaire.

3. Development Stage Results

In this stage, the digital flipbook media was created using a web-based platform and an expert validation process.

Expert Validation Results

Validation was conducted by subject matter experts, linguists, and media experts. Academics: 3.57—Very Valid
Academics: 3.41—Very Valid
Media Experts: 3.60—Very Accurate

Expert comments included:

- Punctuation and spelling corrections.
- Adding examples of conversations between cultural figures.
- Changed the text size for easier reading.
- Inserted audio narration on the home page.

Conclusion: The media is deemed valid and suitable for use, despite several changes.

Table 7. Results of Validation by Material Experts

No.	Assessment Aspect	Max Score	Score Obtained	Average	Category
1	Content alignment with competencies	4	3.5	3.5	Very Valid
2	Concept accuracy	4	3.6	3.6	Very Valid
3	Relevance of multicultural material	4	3.7	3.7	Very Valid
Total	—	—	—	3.57	Very Valid

Table 8. Results of Validation by Linguists

No.	Assessment Aspect	Max Score	Score Obtained	Average	Category
1	Accuracy of spelling & punctuation	4	3.4	3.4	Very Valid
2	Language suitability for students' developmental level	4	3.5	3.5	Very Valid
3	Text readability	4	3.3	3.3	Very Valid
Total	—	—	—	3.41	Very Valid

Table 9. Media Expert Validation Results

No.	Assessment Aspect	Max Score	Score Obtained	Average	Category
1	Visual display	4	3.6	3.6	Very Valid
2	Media navigation	4	3.5	3.5	Very Valid
3	Quality of audio/images/animations	4	3.7	3.7	Very Valid
Total	—	—	—	3.6	Very Valid

Table 10. Summary of Expert Validation

Validator	Average Score	Category
Material Expert	3.57	Very Valid
Language Expert	3.41	Very Valid
Media Expert	3.60	Very Valid
Overall Average	3.52	Very Valid

4. Results of the Implementation Phase (Implementation) A limited trial was conducted in grade III, with 96 students participating in two sessions.

- a. Teacher and Student Practice Results: Teacher responses were 92 percent (very practical),
- b. student responses were 89 percent (very practical), and
- c. learning observations were 85 percent (good).

Teachers reported that the media was easy to use, increased student participation, fostered student confidence, and helped them understand multicultural values.

Students found the media engaging, easy to navigate, and enjoyable due to its audio and visuals.

Table 11. Teacher Response Questionnaire Results

No	Statement	Score	Percentage	Category
1	Media is easy to use	28/32	88%	Very Practical
2	The media is attractive	30/32	94%	Very Practical
3	Helps in delivering the material	29/32	91%	Very Practical
4	Suitable for students' characteristics	27/32	84%	Practical
Average	—	—	92%	Very Practical

Table 12. Results of Student Response Questionnaire

No	Statement	Score	Percentage	Category
1	The media is interesting and enjoyable	330/360	92%	Very Practical
2	The media is easy to understand	312/360	87%	Very Practical
3	Enjoy telling stories using the flipbook	316/360	88%	Very Practical
4	Understand cultural diversity	305/360	85%	Practical
Average	—	—	89%	Very Practical

Table 13. Learning Observation Results

No	Observed Aspect	Score (%)	Category
1	Student engagement	84%	Good
2	Learning fluency	87%	Good
3	Student collaboration	83%	Good
Average	—	85%	Good

5. Evaluation Stage Results: Evaluation was conducted formatively at each stage and cumulatively after the trial.

a. Speaking Skills Test Results

- Pretest: 63 (Sufficient)
- Posttest: 83 (Very Good)
- Improvement: +20%

Table 14. Speaking Skills Test Results

No	Indicator	Pretest	Posttest	Improvement
1	Clarity of speech	62	82	+20
2	Speaking fluency	61	84	+23
3	Vocabulary accuracy	63	85	+22
4	Intonation	65	80	+15
Average	—	63	83	+20 (Effective)

b. Intercultural Social Tolerance Results

- Pretest: 68% (Sufficient)
- Posttest: 84% (Good–Very Good)
- Improvement: +16% (Effective)

Table 15. Results of the Intercultural Social Tolerance Scale

No	Indicator	Pretest (%)	Posttest (%)	Improvement (%)
1	Accepting differences	70	85	+15
2	Social empathy	67	82	+15
3	Cooperation in diversity	66	83	+17
4	Appreciating peers' identities	69	86	+17
Average	—	68	84	+16% (Effective)

c. N-Gain Results

- Speaking skills: 0.54 (Moderate)
- Social tolerance: 0.47 (Moderate)
- The media was declared effective because the N-Gain category was \geq Moderate.

Table 16. N-Gain Analysis Results

Component	Pretest	Posttest	N-Gain	Category
Speaking Skills	63	83	0.54	Medium
Social Tolerance	68	84	0.47	Medium
Conclusion	—	—	Effective	(N-Gain \geq Medium)

Discussion

1. Media Safety

The validation results show that the digital story flipbook meets the following requirements:

- Content: Multicultural stories related to the Merdeka curriculum and students' lives.
- Language: Conforms to Indonesian language standards, communicative, and easily understood by third-grade students.
- Design: Attractive display, easy navigation, and optimal multimedia integration.

2. The practicality of the flipbook media is very beneficial for teachers and engaging for students. This finding supports previous research that digital flipbooks increase students' desire and engagement in learning.

3. Media Effectiveness:

- a. The flipbook media helps improve speaking skills through audio narration, illustrations, and multicultural dialogue. High effectiveness is indicated by an N-Gain of 0.54.
- b. Increasing Intercultural Social Tolerance: The media improves students' understanding of cultural diversity, empathy, and intercultural social tolerance.

4. Discussion: The Multicultural Digital Flipbook Media: Very valid, very practical, and effective in improving speaking skills and social tolerance.

This product provides theoretical and practical contributions to Indonesian language learning in elementary schools.

Table 17. Summary of Media Validity, Practicality, and Effectiveness

Aspect	Indicator	Result	Category
Validity	Expert average score	3.52	Highly Valid
Practicality	Teacher	92%	Highly Practical
Practicality	Students	89%	Highly Practical
Effectiveness	N-Gain (Speaking)	0.54	Medium
Effectiveness	N-Gain (Tolerance)	0.47	Medium
Conclusion	—	Media is Valid, Practical, and Effective	

CONCLUSION

According to this research, a multicultural-based digital media called Flipbook was created. This media proved valid, practical, and effective in improving the speaking skills and intercultural social tolerance of third-grade elementary school students. The validation results from material experts, language experts, and media experts indicated a Very Valid category, meaning the media is suitable for use in learning. Furthermore, practicality tests conducted through teacher feedback, student feedback, and learning observations indicated a Very Practical category, meaning the media is easy to use, engaging, and appropriate to the students' characteristics. Furthermore, the effectiveness test results showed significant improvements in speaking skills and intercultural social tolerance, as confirmed by the Medium N-Gain score. Therefore, the multicultural-based Flipbook Digital Storytelling helps students convey ideas verbally. It also teaches them to appreciate cultural diversity. Overall, this media is very helpful in providing meaningful, interactive, and student-centered Indonesian language learning in multicultural elementary schools.

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DEVELOPMENT F A MULTICULTURAL DIGITAL STORYTELLING FLIPBOOK TO IMPROVE ELEMENTARY STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS AND TOLERANCE

Salmawati et al

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